

Steering framework for services in NFDI4Objects

1. Fundamentals and objectives

- **Objective:** To strengthen the German science system through a reliable and transparent research data infrastructure in the field of material cultural assets. Infrastructures are understood to mean the organisational, professional and technical interaction of decentralised, specialist services offered by different actors.
- **Demand orientation:** The needs of the scientific community are the focus. Flexible structures are necessary to meet changing requirements.
- **Quality assurance:** Establishment of comprehensive quality management to ensure the development, operation and sustainability of services.
- **Sustainability:** Long-term operating and financing models that guarantee the reliability and stability of the infrastructure.
- **Interoperability:** Ensuring the interoperability of data and services through common architectures and standards.
- **Connectivity:** Ensuring national and international connectivity by establishing standards.

2. Organisational structure and roles

2.1. Steering committee

- A steering committee monitors compliance with the joint work plan and cooperation agreement.
- It makes strategic decisions, particularly with regard to the further development of service management and service portfolio management in N4O, as well as the associated steps and measures for quality assurance.
- The Steering Committee ensures compliance with the "Guidelines for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice" and the FAIR principles.
- The chair of the steering committee acts as **the managing director**. In this role, he/she is also responsible for the overall strategic direction of service management and service portfolio management in N4O.

2.2. Service Portfolio Development (as a Community Cluster)

- N4O requires a working group that is responsible for sustainable service-specific quality criteria for the service portfolio. There are no comparable working groups in the current N4O structures; we therefore recommend that such working groups be set up in N4O under the name "Special Interest Group" (initiated in the current application phase by a community cluster, which can be converted into a SIG in the event of regular operation), which can later be managed independently by the Service Monitoring Team (see 2.4).
- A Community Cluster "Service Portfolio Development" is to serve as a **cross-thematic think tank** to prepare strategies for **quality management** and **sustainability**, the **definition of KPIs** and the establishment of a **monitoring system** for the certification board and steering committee.
- This would make the CC/SIG the unit responsible for developing **proposals for quality criteria** in N4O, which **would** then **be adopted** in the regular **Commons process**.

2.3. Coordinator

- The coordinator is responsible for **coordinating activities** to implement the strategy and for continuous quality assurance of services.
- The coordinator must be supported by dedicated staff resources. This task should be performed by the coordination office as part of ongoing project funding.
- The coordinator acts as a **quality officer**. In this role, he/she manages quality management and acts as an interface between management and service providers.

2.4. Service Monitoring Team

- This committee organises the processes of service control and service portfolio management in N4O, i.e. the evaluation, monitoring and review of services with the aim of including, confirming or excluding them from the N4O service portfolio (onboarding, recertification, offboarding). To this end, it is in contact with the respective service managers, i.e. those persons who are responsible for an individual service that is or is to become part of the N4O infrastructure.
- It comprises the coordinator and members from all task areas in order to reflect the technical diversity and expertise in service quality management.
- Together with those responsible for the services, the committee selects a service category (according to the defined list) that defines the primary set of milestones or specific quality criteria/KPIs.
- Based on the approved quality criteria, it prepares all relevant information and documents for the certification process and submits them to the certification board for review and decision.

2.5. Certification Board

- The certification board is responsible for **formal quality assurance**.
- It consists of the coordinator, members of the service monitoring team and an independent procedural officer who ensures that processes and procedures are carried out correctly.
- The members of the Certification Board act as **quality auditors** and carry out audits to check compliance with the quality criteria.
- The board makes final decisions on the inclusion or rejection of services in the portfolio, i.e. the N4O certification of services. It also takes into account the interaction of different services, especially when new services are added or existing services are discontinued. It may impose conditions and allow a new submission for decision.

3. Processes and procedures

3.1. Fundamentals: Quality management strategy

- The quality management strategy comprises **three phases**: onboarding, monitoring and review.
- **Primary quality objective**: Establishment of the N4O consortium as a reliable infrastructure provider.
- **Development objectives**: Consideration of the consortium's resources and stage of development, gradual development of quality management.
- **Quality objectives**: Ensuring a uniform level of quality, external branding through strong user support and internal support for partner institutions.
- **Types of services**: Subdivision of services into "technical services", "community services" and "support and consulting" in order to meet specific quality requirements.

- **Quality assurance and control:** Onboarding and evaluation, ongoing monitoring, performance review.

3.2. Definition of quality criteria

- Proposals are developed by CC/SIG "Service Portfolio Development" (see 2.2 above)
- Approval in General Assembly as a Commons process
- Possible points for criteria:

3.2.1 Criteria for successful onboarding

- The quality criteria cover technical, organisational and administrative aspects.
- Examples: Non-commercial, sufficient documentation, runnability on current systems.
- Proof of community involvement in the development of services is an important criterion.
- Existing standards and certificates (e.g. CoreTrustSeal) are taken into account.

3.2.2 Criteria: Documentation and communication

- The **service profiles** are documented centrally and made accessible to all parties involved.
- **Instructions and templates** are provided for those responsible for or operating the services.
- The **communication strategy** informs users about news and developments (e.g. newsletter, website).
- The services are registered on relevant platforms.

3.2.3 Criteria: Financing and sustainability

- The services are financed by basic **institutional funding** and **project funds**.
- A **business/organisational model** is developed to secure long-term funding.
- The **sustainability assessment** takes into account the costs and models, considering the working conditions of the institutions.
- **Open source licences** for software and services are promoted.

3.3. Onboarding of services

- Those responsible for the services fill out a **form** in which all relevant information must be entered.
- The form is used to generate a **service profile** that contains information for users, particularly with regard to service control, service portfolio management and service monitoring.
- Those responsible for the services provide helpdesk contacts and materials for public relations work.
- Compilation of all relevant information and documents by the Service Monitoring Team.
- This is submitted to the certification board for **formal review** of the services based on defined quality criteria and for a **final decision**.
- In the event of requirements formulated by the certification board, these are communicated to the service monitoring team. The service managers are responsible for resubmitting the certification. The rest of the process corresponds to the regular onboarding process.
- **Communication** of successful certifications is managed both internally and externally.

3.4. Service Portfolio Monitoring

- **Service quality** is continuously monitored using quantitative (KPIs) and qualitative measures.
- **KPIs** are defined for each service category to measure the performance and quality of the services.
- The results of the monitoring are visualised in a **dashboard**.

- The **service monitoring team** selects the primary KPI sets together with those responsible for the services.

3.5. Service review (recertification & offboarding)

- All services listed in the N4O service portfolio are reviewed regularly, at least **every two years**, to verify their ongoing compliance with quality criteria.
- If updates or further developments are made to a service that significantly change its properties, features, functionalities or type of operation, for example, these services are also subject to review. Those responsible for the services are required to report such changes independently to the Service Monitoring Team.
- A service may also be reviewed if community feedback suggests that significant changes have been made.
- The review of a service is carried out in terms of process flow and criteria in the same way as regular onboarding (see 3.3).
- If a service no longer meets the required quality criteria or only meets them to an insufficient extent, the certification board decides on conditions that must be met within a specified period in order to retain N4O certification. If these conditions are not met, the certificate awarded is revoked and the service is removed from the N4O service portfolio.

4. Conclusion

This management concept for services in N4O is intended to provide a solid foundation for developing a high-quality, sustainable infrastructure for research in the field of material cultural heritage. By focusing on proven methods, a clear structure and the integration of quality management, N4O can best meet the needs of the scientific community and make an important contribution to Germany's digital sovereignty.